

Alternative to Fermat's Principle for a Moving Mirror?

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In (1) the problem of a light reflecting from a mirror moving at constant v in the negative y direction is considered. The incident ray makes an angle AA with the y axis and the reflected, an angle BB with the y axis. Fermat's principle is used i.e. the minimization of time moving from point A , reflecting from the moving mirror and moving to point B (with A and B being at the same y value). A relationship is found linking $\cos(BB)$ to $\cos(AA)$.

In this note we try to argue that the same relationship follows from considering a constant horizontal velocity H along the x axis with relative velocities of light and the mirror (for the incident and reflected cases) representing adjacent projections of H i.e. H serves as a hypotenuse.

Fermat's Principle Following (1)

Consider a mirror moving in the negative y direction with a velocity v . At time $t=0$, the incident ray is at $y=d_0$ and makes an angle of AA with the y axis. Eventually the ray hits the mirror. It makes a triangle with d_0+vt_a along the y axis, ct_a as the hypotenuse and x (along the x axis) with t_a being time. It then reflects and moves to B which is at the same y value as A . A second triangle is made with ct_b as the hypotenuse, $L-x$ as the x length and d_0+vt_a as the y length.

In (1) the total time traveled t_a+t_b is calculated in terms of t_a , L , x , v and c and minimized with respect to x ($d/dx F = 0$). The details are given in (1) and are not lengthy. The main result is that:

$$\sin(AA) - \sin(BB) = -v/c \sin(AA+BB) \quad ((1))$$

(This is then written in the form: $\cos(BB) = \text{Function}(\cos(AA), v, c)$).

The objective of this note is to examine whether ((1)) may be obtained more directly using a principle other than that of Fermat's.

Alternative Principle for Light Reflecting from a Moving Mirror

Light moves from point A on the left to point B on the right, thus there is a flow from left to right and moreover a horizontal (along x) flow which does not involve any interaction. We use this as a motivation.

Consider ((1)) written as:

$$\sin(AA) \{ c + v\cos(BB) \} = \sin(BB) \{ c - v\cos(AA) \} \quad ((2))$$

$c+v\cos(BB)$ is the relative velocity of the reflected ray i.e. the velocity in the negative y direction is broken into components parallel and perpendicular to the ray. Likewise $c-v\cos(AA)$ is the relative velocity of the incoming ray. ((2)) is of the form of:

$$H \sin(AA) = \{ c - v\cos(AA) \} \quad \text{and} \quad H \sin(BB) = \{ c + v\cos(BB) \}$$

One may note that the incident ray makes an angle of $90\text{deg} - AA$ with the horizontal and the reflected an angle of $90\text{deg} - BB$ with the horizontal (i.e. x).

$$H \sin(AA) = H \cos(90-AA) \quad \text{and} \quad H \sin(BB) = H \cos(90-BB)$$

Thus H (which is a hypothetical velocity along the x direction) acts as a hypotenuse with the relative velocities of the incident and reflected rays being adjacent sides to the angle $90-AA$ or $90-BB$.

As a result, it seems that one may directly obtain ((1)) using the idea of a constant H velocity in the x direction instead of Fermat's principle. One must, however, use relative velocities and treat the incident and reflected rays as adjacent sides with H as a hypotenuse.

Momentum in the X Direction

One may ask: Should momentum of the light in the x direction be conserved as there is no interaction in this direction. For Snell's law (2), conservation of momentum in the x direction is used and it seems that the same should be applied in this problem.

First one should note that the result obtained using Fermat's principle i.e. $\cos(BB) = \text{Function}(\cos(AA))$ is used to obtain a relationship between $p(\text{incident})$ and $p(\text{reflected})$ in (3).

We consider the results here to see if horizontal momentum of the light is conserved i.e. if

$$1/(\text{wavelength reflected}) \sin(BB) = 1/(\text{wavelength initial}) \sin(AA)$$

We use from (1) with $c=1$:

$$\cos(BB) = \{-2v + (1+vv) \cos(AA)\} / \{1 - 2v\cos(AA) + vv\}$$

We use the result from (3)

$$\text{Wavelength reflected} / \text{wavelength incident} = (1-vv) / \{1-2v\cos(AA) + vv\}$$

We then find that the x-momentum projection of the incident ray equals the x-projection of the momentum of the reflected ray.

Conclusion

In conclusion we suggest that there may be an alternative, more direct, method to Fermat's for obtaining a relationship between incident and reflected angles of light reflected from a mirror moving at a constant v in the negative y direction. Fermat's principle minimizes time as the light moves from A ($x=0, y=d_0$), hits the mirror at point x and then moves to B ($x=L, y=d_0$). This requires performing a d/dx operation on a function of x representing the overall time.

We suggest one may use the notion of a constant hypothetical H velocity in the x direction with the relative velocities (light and mirror along the light motion) representing adjacent projections and H a hypotenuse. This leads immediately to the main result of the Fermat approach and seems to be based on the physical idea of continuity along the x direction (for which there is no interaction).

References

1. Gjurchinovski, A. Einstein's Mirror and Fermat's Principle of Least Time (Am. J. of Physics, Vol 72, No 10 Oct 2004)
http://muj.optol.cz/~richterek/data/media/ref_str/gjurchinovski2004.pdf